

Constraints to Urban Agriculture for Sustainable Food Production in Port-Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State

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Abstract

The study identified the constraints to urban agriculture for sustainable food production in port-harcourt metropolis, Rivers state. Three research questions and three hypotheses guided the study. The study was carried out in Port Harcourt Metropolis, in Rivers State. Port Harcourt is the capital and largest city of Rivers State, Nigeria. Founded 1912 and incorporated in 1913, it is located in the rich Niger Delta region and lies along the Bonny River. Port Harcourt Metropolis is made up of four (4) local governments areas (Port Harcourt, Obio/Akpor, Okrika and Eleme) with a population of about 2,344,000 (en.m.wikipedia.org). The study adopted a descriptive survey research design. The target population was all (infinite population) urban farmers in Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State. A simple random sampling technique was adopted to select 46 females and 30 males from the four (4) local government areas (Port Harcourt, Obio/Akpor, Okrika and Eleme) in the study area. The instrument for data collection was a structured questionnaire designed in a 4-point rating scale of agreement which was validated by two experts. The reliability of the instrument was established using Cronbach alpha reliability coefficient method which yielded a reliability coefficient (r) of 0.83. Data obtained were analyzed using mean and standard deviation with an accepted mean value of 2.50 and above. The findings showed that poor infrastructural resources, poor environmental conditions and intellectual skills of the urban farmers hinder the achievement of urban agriculture for sustainable food production. Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended that the government and NGO's should provide farming skills acquisition center to teach modern practices to urban farmers in order to transmit knowledge of new production methods to enhance sustainable food production.

Keywords: Constraints, Urban Agriculture, Sustainable Food Production

INTRODUCTION

Food Production is a key area that requires action alongside issues of food consumption, nutrition and food security. According to FAO (2009), it is estimated that by 2050, the world will reach 9.1 billion (34% higher than today). Food Production will need to increase by 70% to be able to feed the larger and most likely urban population. More food will have to have to be produced using less land. It becomes necessary therefore to ensure a sustainable food supply for the world's fast-growing population.

Sustainable food production refers to the production of food that will meet the requirement of today using safe healthy methods and processes without compromising the need of future generation (Foresight, 2011). Sustainable food production involves production methods using processes and systems that are non-polluting, conserve non-renewable energy and natural resources, economically, efficient, safe for workers, communities and consumers, and do not compromise the needs of future generations. Sustainable food production necessitates the practice of urban agriculture.

Urban agriculture refers to the cultivation of crops and rearing of animals within or on the fringe of metropolis either for family consumption or commercialization. FAO (2019) viewed urban agriculture as a sustainable and innovative approach to agriculture which aims at addressing issues such as food insecurity, limited access to fresh produce and environmental sustainability in cities. Urban agriculture can take the form of vertical farming, hydroponics, aeroponics, and rooftop gardens. These forms allow for the cultivation of variety of crops, including vegetables, herbs, fruits and fish in aquaponics system (Crush, 2014).

Urban agriculture (UA) comprises of a range of activities such as the production, processing, marketing and distribution of agricultural produce in the urban setting (Orsini, et al, 2013). UA provides employment opportunities to urban residents in varying forms and degrees across the world. In the global north, urban agriculture is practiced on a wide range of land areas such as allotments, private domestic gardens (Foster, et al, 2017). Crops grown include fruits and vegetables (Orsini, et al, 2013). In the global south, urban food production is practiced on private owned or rented land, vacant or open spaces, houses as well as rivers, ponds and lakes (Ibitaye et al, 2016).

There is a contrasting motivation for practicing urban agriculture across the globe. Urban agriculture is practiced mainly for recreational or social purposes in the global north and in the global south countries, urban agriculture is practiced mainly for food security and poverty alleviation (Zezza & Tasciotti, 2016). Urban agriculture is gaining popularity in many countries in the world. Salan and Attah (2012) observed that urban agriculture contributes to household food availability and dietary diversity. As a livelihood strategy, Binns and Nel (2019) noted that urban agriculture provides significant employment opportunities for both urban farmers and other services providers along the supply chains. In terms of its environmental impact, urban agriculture contributes to the reduction of energy use and greenhouse gas emission. (De Zeeuw et al, 2011). Furthermore, trees maintained on land for urban agriculture contribute to urban environment and serve as adaptive and mitigation measures. Despite the contributions of urban agriculture and its importance in securing food for urban dwellers, urban agriculture is constrained by such factors as lack of infrastructural resources, intellectual problems and environmental problems.

Urban infrastructural resource such as Farming Skill Acquisition Centre (FSAC) is necessary for inculcating life skills that will enable urban farmers increase production. Amadi and Aleru, (2020) observed that Farming Skill Acquisition Centre is a major infrastructure that develops urban farmers' skill on the adoption of improved methods in crop and livestock production in order to meet market demand and earn income for the family. Farming Skills Acquisition Centre is the basis on which urban farming community will be made to experience increased and sustainable food production.

Lack of farming skill acquisition Centre will restrain urban farmers' financial ability and general business skills that will enable them have deep understanding of agricultural production (Fiala, 2018). Provision of urban infrastructure will enable urban farmers learn different skills in processing varieties of agricultural produce, thereby increasing their productivity and income. Emeshu (2008) affirmed that provision of agricultural production skill training centre improves business practice of farmer-owned enterprises. Learning new methods of crop and livestock production encourages farmers to adopt new techniques hence creating jobs for others. Olukotun (2007) stated that urban farmers look more to the government for the provision of good roads, electricity, good water supply and health care centre in order to produce sustainable food.

Modern market promotes improved standard of living of urban farmers. The urban market exists to facilitate urban farmers' exchange of agricultural products. It serves as an avenue for the reconciliation of demand and supply of farm produce to enhance sustainable food production. However, the market is mostly constrained by leaking roofs, environmental hazard and small nature of space. Nyako (2016) pointed that government should intervene and create a more suitable environment for agribusiness among urban farmers. Provision of modern markets increases urban farmers' income and fosters economic growth for sustainable food production.

Provision of good accessible roads is important to enhance the urban farmers' easy distribution of farm produce. Olukotun (2007) stated that good accessible roads are important for farmers' evacuation of agricultural products, marketing of farm produce and the delivery of improved farm inputs for increased food production and income for urban farmers.

Environmentally, UA is constrained by factors that impact its feasibility and sustainability. Edeoghon and Izekor (2017) identified poor access to land as a constraining factor to the development of UA in Nigeria. Fragne et al (2014) argued that access to land and other resources are necessary preconditions for U.A to deliver benefits to households including urban food security. Relating to poor access to land is the conflicting use of land for development and agricultural purposes and the rapid urbanization stimulated by rural-urban migration and population growth leading to a decline in the available prime urban agricultural land (Onyebueke et al. 2020). Poor access to land in the urban areas affect large scale agriculture.

Odewumi et al (2018) in their study on U.A in Ibadan Metropolis, South-Western Nigeria, found the negative effect of climate change on UA as water scarcity, disease outbreaks and delays in harvesting periods. The survey on urban farmers reported that their farming activities were negatively affected by the unpredictable rainfall, pest and disease outbreaks and heat stresses resulting in decreased farm yield and income. According to Asadu et al (2016), the environmental constraints confronting farmers in their attempt to gain access to farmland in the urban areas include vulnerability to theft, crop damage by passing livestock, poor soil quality, limited space, water scarcity and contamination resulting from industrial and urban waste.

Intellectual constraints refer to lack of/non-acquisition of skills that are vital for urban farmers' effectiveness in production agriculture. Sustainable food production ability of the urban farmers depends solely on the level of

knowledge and awareness possessed in agricultural production. (Amaoli and Alem, 2020). Intellectual resources of farmers are the information and skills that an urban farmer acquires through training or experiences (Onu, Jimoh, Ifeanyieze, Nwankwo, Onah, Ekenta & Ezebuio, 2018). Urban farmers need to be taught skills to perform specific task in agricultural production for the achievement of sustainable food production. Farm inputs, methods and technologies are required by urban farmers to boost production, hence, the need for farming skill training for improved knowledge in the adoption of machinery, fertilizers, and herbicides to maximize profits. Nnodim and Aleru (2020) affirmed that farmers need to be trained on skills that address their needs and prepare them for agribusiness hence, training urban farmers on managerial skills, innovativeness, awareness of new farm inputs and effective decision-making skills becomes very necessary.

Farming skill training is necessary for improving urban farmers' capacity for innovativeness, creativity, and productivity. Urban farmers need to develop skills in soil management, processing, marketing, distribution and food storage for sustainable production. Most farmers lack the knowledge of what to produce and how to sustain their production hence, urban farmers need training skills that will enable them determine what to produce and how to achieve sustainable food production. According to Amadi and Aleru (2020) Farmer's leadership skills enhance his effectiveness in the organization and operation of a farm business on a continuing basis and to abreast change in method. Thus, the acquisition of leadership training skills by urban farmers is necessary to achieve sustainable food production through innovation and production networking system.

Statement of problem

Urban agriculture is important for the provision of food, fruits and vegetables. It also provides significant employment opportunities for both urban farmers and other services providers along the supply chains. In terms of its environmental impact, urban agriculture contributes to the reduction of energy use and greenhouse gas emission. (De Zeeuw et al, 2011). Furthermore, trees maintained on land for urban agriculture contribute to urban environment and serve as adaptive and mitigation measures. Despite the contributions of urban agriculture and its importance in securing food for urban dwellers, urban agriculture is not highly practiced in the urban areas probably due to some constraining factors and this poses problems on food production. If food production is to be sustained in the urban areas, urban farmers need to identify the constraining factors in order to practice agriculture to achieve sustainable food production. Hence, this study intends to identify the constraints to urban agriculture for sustainable food production in Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State.

Purpose of the study

The main purpose of the study was to identify the constraints to urban agriculture for sustainable food production in Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Identity the infrastructural constraints to urban agriculture in Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State.
2. Ascertain the environmental constraints to urban agriculture for sustainable food production in Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State.
3. Determine the intellectual constraints to urban agriculture in Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State.

Research Questions

The study was guided by the following research questions:

1. What are the infrastructural constraints to urban agriculture for sustainable food production in Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State?
2. What are the environmental constraints to urban agriculture for sustainable food production in Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State?
3. What are the intellectual constraints to urban agriculture for sustainable food production in Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State?

METHODOLOGY

The study was carried out in Port Harcourt Metropolis, in Rivers State. Port Harcourt is the capital and largest city of Rivers State, Nigeria. Founded 1912 and incorporated in 1913, it is located in the rich Niger Delta region and lies along the Bonny River. Port Harcourt Metropolis is made up of four (4) local governments areas (Port Harcourt, Obio/Akpor, Okrika and Eleme) with a population of about 2,344,000 (en.m.wikipedia.org). The study adopted a descriptive survey research design. The target population was all (infinite population) urban farmers in Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State. A simple random sampling technique was adopted to select 46 females and 30 males from

the four (4) local government areas (Port Harcourt, Obio/Akpor, Okrika and Eleme) in the study area. The instrument for data collection was a structured questionnaire designed in a 4-point rating scale of agreement which was validated by two experts. The reliability of the instrument was established using Cronbach alpha reliability coefficient method which yielded a reliability coefficient (r) of 0.83. Data obtained were analyzed using mean and standard deviation with an accepted mean value of 2.50 and above.

RESULT

Research Question 1: What are the infrastructural constraints to urban agriculture for sustainable food production in Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State?

Table 1: Mean responses on infrastructural constraints to urban agriculture for sustainable food production in Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State.

S/N	Item	Men		Decision	Women		Decision
		X ₁	SD		X ₂	SD	
1	Lack of farming skills acquisition centre to teach modern practices to urban farmers hinders sustainable food production.	3.53	0.56	Agree	3.91	0.68	Agree
2	Unstable electricity for crop processing and brooding of chicks leads to inadequate food production and supply.	3.42	0.64	Agree	3.52	0.67	Agree
3	Lack of modern markets hinders the efficient distribution and exchange of goods and services in promoting sustainable food production.	3.32	0.80	Agree	3.46	0.68	Agree
4	Inadequate farm processing centre for processing different crop varieties affects sustainable food production.	3.20	0.82	Agree	3.60	0.78	Agree
5	Poor road network affects the transportation and distribution of urban farm produce to markets hence creating food scarcity.	3.62	0.81	Agree	3.71	0.53	Agree
6	Lack of quality water sources for irrigation affect the growth and productivity of urban farm crops for sustainable food production	2.91	0.62	Agree	3.24	0.67	Agree
7	Lack of storage facilities to preserve urban farmers' crops leads to wastage of urban farm produce thereby affecting food availability.	3.52	0.86	Agree	3.09	0.76	Agree
8	Inadequate extension service facilities hinder urban farmers from adopting new methods of food production for sustainability.	3.42	0.62	Agree	3.87	0.50	Agree
9	Non-availability of credit and finance facilities limits the ability of farmers to invest in their farms for sustainable food production.	3.65	0.86	Agree	3.23	0.90	Agree
		3.40	0.73		3.51	0.69	

Table 1 shows the mean and standard deviation of respondents on infrastructural constraints to urban agriculture for sustainable food production in Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State. The respondents agreed that lack of farming skills acquisition center to teach modern practices to urban farmers limits farmers' knowledge of new production methods to enhance sustainable food production (3.53 & 3.91), Unstable electricity leads to poor crop processing and brooding of chicks (3.42 & 3.52), Lack of efficient distribution and exchange of goods and services hence, affecting sustainable food production (3.32 & 3.46), Inadequate farm processing center for processing different crop varieties affects the forms and packaging of urban farm produce (3.22 & 3.60), Poor road network affects the transportation and distribution of urban farm produce (3.62 & 3.71), Lack of quality water source for irrigation affects the growth and productivity of urban farm crops (2.91 & 3.24), Lack of storage facilities to preserve urban farmers' produce leads to wastage urban farm produce (3.52 & 3.09), Inadequate extension service facilities hinder urban farmers from adopting new methods of food production (3.42 & 3.87), Non-availability of credit and finance facilities limits the

ability of urban farmers to invest in their farms for sustainable food production (3.65 & 3.23). Table 1 shows low standard deviation scores which indicates that the datasets were not widely spread out.

Research Question 2. What are the environmental constraints to urban agriculture for sustainable food production in Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State?

Table 2: Mean responses on environmental constraints to urban agriculture for sustainable food production in Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State.

S/N	Items	Men			Women		
		Mean	S.D	Rmrk	Mean	S.D	Rmk
1	Inadequate land space to rapid urbanization and high population growth affects urban agriculture.	3.86	0.52	Agree	3.18	0.70	Agree
2	Poor access to improved agricultural inputs limits sustainable food productivity.	3.08	0.92	Agree	3.67	0.65	Agree
3	Conflicting use of urban land for non-agricultural purposes affects food production.	3.55	0.63	Agree	3.54	0.92	Agree
4	Most equipment and tools not suited for urban agriculture hence, small scale production of food.	3.34	0.81	Agree	2.74	1.07	Agree
5	Lack of access to ground water and sewage results to poor crop yield thereby affecting food security.	3.78	0.87	Agree	3.63	0.60	Agree
6	Soil contamination resulting from industrial and urban waste usually leads to poor yield of crops.	3.04	0.56	Agree	3.64	1.07	Agree
7	Air and noise pollution caused by heavy-duty machines poses threat to livestock and poultry thereby reducing their productivity.	2.78	0.80	Agree	3.01	0.98	Agree
8	Inadequate water for irrigation affects crop yield for sustainable food production.	3.03	0.57	Agree	3.19	0.85	Agree
		3.31	0.71		3.33	0.86	

Table 2 shows the mean and standard deviation of respondents on environmental constraints to urban agriculture for sustainable food production in Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State. The respondents agreed that inadequate land space due to rapid urbanization and high population growth affect urban agriculture (3.08 & 3.18), Poor access to improved agricultural inputs limit sustainable food production (3.08 & 3.67), Conflicting use of urban land for non-agricultural purposes affect food production (3.55 & 3.54), Most equipment and tools not suited for urban agriculture hinders large scale agriculture leading to small scale agriculture/food production (3.34 & 2.74), Lack of access to ground water and sewage results to poor crop yield (3.78 & 3.64), Soil contamination resulting from industrial and urban waste usually leads to poor yield of crops (3.04 & 3.64), Air and noise pollution caused by heavy-duty machines poses threat to livestock and poultry production thereby hindering food production (2.78 & 3.01), inadequate water for irrigation affect crop yield thereby limiting sustainable food production (3.03 & 3.19). Table 2 shows low standard deviation scores which indicates that the datasets were not widely spread out.

Research Question 3. What are the intellectual constraints to urban agriculture for sustainable food production in Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State?

Table 3: Mean responses on intellectual constraints to urban agriculture for sustainable food production in Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State.

S/N	Items	Men			Women		
		Mean	S.D	Rmk	Mean	S.D	Rmk
1	Urban farmers lack decision-making skills on adoption of improved farm inputs/methods for sustainable food production.	3.20	0.82	Agree	3.03	0.70	Agree
2	poor knowledge of the urban farmers on innovativeness affect urban farmers idea in crop/livestock production.	3.80	0.54	Agree	3.79	0.92	Agree
3	Poor managerial ability to improve agricultural skills/methods affect crop/animal productivity.	3.56	0.54	Agree	3.43	0.97	Agree
4	Cooperative and networking skills limits urban farmers to connect with others in promoting sustainable food production.	3.01	0.68	Agree	3.86	0.50	Agree
5	Poor production skills of urban farmers to increase output in farm produce to enhance food security.	3.22	0.79	Agree	3.87	0.42	Agree
6	Urban farmers poor marketing skills, affect the distribution of agricultural produce to the target consumers.	3.22	0.71	Agree	3.86	0.65	Agree
7	Poor knowledge of urban farmers on improved production competence methods to achieve sustainable food production.	3.59	0.69	Agree	3.67	0.63	Agree
8	Lack of urban farmers organizational capacity to maximize profits in farm business for sustainable food production.	3.62	0.77	Agree	3.45	0.83	Agree
9	Lack of farm produce processing skills to enhance food preservation.	0.99	3.54	Agree	1.01	3.41	Agree
Grand Mean and StD		3.40	0.73		3.61	0.73	

Table 3 shows the mean and standard deviation of respondents on intellectual constraints to urban agriculture for sustainable food production in Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State. The respondents agreed that urban farmers' lack of decision-making skills on adoption of improved farm inputs/methods for sustainable food production (3.20 & 3.03), Poor knowledge of the urban farmers on innovativeness affect improved idea in crop/livestock production (3.56 & 3.43), Poor managerial ability to improve agricultural skills/methods affects crop/animal productivity (3.80 & 3.79), Lack of cooperative and networking skills limits urban farmers' ability to connect with others in promoting sustainable food production (3.41 & 3.54), Poor production skills of the urban farmers reduces output in farm produce thereby affecting food production (3.59 & 3.67), Urban farmers' lack of skills in marketing affects the distribution of agricultural produce to the target consumer (3.62 & 3.45), Urban farmers' lack of competence on improved production methods affects the achievement of sustainable food production (3.22 & 3.87), Lack of organizational capacity to maximize profits in farm business limits the achievement of sustainable food production (3.22 & 3.86), Lack of farm produce processing skills hinders sustainable food production (3.01 & 3.86). Table 3 revealed low standard deviation scores which indicates that the datasets were not widely dispersed.

Discussion of findings

Findings from research question 1 showed that lack of farming acquisition centre, unstable electricity, lack of modern markets, inadequate farm processing center, poor road network, lack of quality water source, lack of storage facilities, inadequate extension service facilities and non-availability of credit and finance facilities are some of infrastructural constraints to urban agriculture for sustainable food production in Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State. Unavailability of infrastructural resources hinders urban farmer's productivity hence inadequate food supply. This agrees with Fiala (2018) that lack of farming skill acquisition centre will restrain urban farmers financial ability and general business skills that will enable them have deep understanding of agricultural production. The study also agrees with Olukotun (2007) who asserted that urban farmers look more to the government for the provision of good roads, electricity, good water supply and health care center in order to achieve sustainable food supply.

Research question 2 indicated that inadequate land space due to rapid urbanization and high population growth, poor access to improved agricultural inputs, conflicting use of urban land for non-agricultural purposes, most equipment and tools not suited for urban agriculture, lack of access to good ground water and sewage, soil contamination resulting from industrial and urban waste, air and noise pollution caused by heavy-duty machines, inadequate water for irrigation are the environmental constraints to urban agriculture for sustainable food production in Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State.

Research question 3 identified urban farmers' lack of decision-making skills, poor managerial ability, poor knowledge on innovativeness, lack of farm produce processing skills, lack of competence, lack of organizational capacity, poor production skills, poor marketing skills and lack of cooperative and networking skills as the intellectual constraints to urban agriculture for sustainable food production in Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State. The findings conform with Nnodim and Aleru (2020) that urban farmers need to be trained on managerial skills, innovativeness, awareness of farm inputs and effective decision-making skills in order to prepare them for agribusiness. The study also agrees with Amadi and Aleru (2020) that farmer's leadership skill enhances his effectiveness in the organization and operations of a farm business on a continuing basis and to abreast change in method.

CONCLUSION

The study concluded that poor infrastructural resources, poor environmental conditions and intellectual skills of the urban farmers hinder the achievement of urban agriculture for sustainable food production. Thus, the provision of infrastructural resources, suitable environment and urban farmer's acquisition of intellectual skills will enhance sustainable food production in Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings, the following were recommended:

1. The government and NGO's should provide farming skills acquisition center to teach modern practices to urban farmers in order to transmit knowledge of new production methods to enhance sustainable food production.
2. The government and stake holders should provide land for agricultural purposes in the urban areas to enhance sustainable food production. Also, equipment and tools suited for urban agriculture should be produced/provided to enhance large scale urban farming and food production.
3. Urban farmers should be trained to adopt improved farm inputs/methods for sustainable food production. Also, urban farmers should be trained to acquire skills on innovativeness and managerial ability for improved agricultural methods to enhance crop/animal productivity.

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